

**DASTURLASHTIRISHDA INTERFAOL TA'LIM SOHASIDA
ZAMONAVIY TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH
ISTIQBOLLARI**

Usmonov Maxsud Tulqin o'g'li

Mirzo Ulug'bek nomidagi O'zbekiston Milliy universiteti, 1-bosqich magistrant.

maqsudu32@gmail.com

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Annotatsiya. Universitet va maktabda dasturlashni o'qitish metodikasini takomillashtirish muammosi o'rganilmoqda. Talabalarning jamoaviy ishlashi, multimedia kontenti, virtual makon va boshqalar bilan bog'liq yangi o'qitish uslub va shakllari zarurligi asoslab berilgan. Yetakchi xorijiy oliy o'quv yurtlarida dasturlashni o'qitish amaliyoti tahlil qilingan va o'zbek tilida dasturlashni o'qitishni takomillashtirishning asosiy yo'llari. ta'lim muassasalari taklif etiladi. Muallif dasturlashni o'rgatish bo'yicha o'z tajribasini taqdim etadi va ilg'or texnologiyalarni yoyish maqsadida dasturlashni o'rgatishning an'anaviy yondashuvlari va informatika o'qitish usullarini pedagogika universitetlarida o'zgartirishni boshlashni taklif qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: dasturlash, o'qitish usullari, loyiha faoliyati, jamoaviy ish, interaktiv texnologiyalar, Internet platformasi, o'qituvchilar malakasini oshirish, robototexnika, mobil ilovalar, algoritm, dastur, elektron ta'lim resursi.

Аннотация. Рассматривается компьютеризация обучения, которая положительно влияет на все компоненты современной системы образования (цель, содержание, метод, технология) и порождает необходимость их освоения. Исследуются вопросы внедрения компьютерных технологий в преподавание графических дисциплин. Проблемы, вытекающие из этого, и поиск возможных путей их решения. Даны выводы о необходимости разработки интегрированного курса геометрического моделирования, инженерии и компьютерной графики и унифицированных методических подходов к использованию компьютерной техники в учебном процессе, адаптации содержания курса "компьютерная графика", применяемого к блоку общепрофессиональных дисциплин с учетом междисциплинарных связей.

Ключевые слова: 3ds Max, Blender, GoogleSketchUp, карта сознания, DiagrammaName, ArtRage.

Abstract. The article considers the computerization of education, which positively affects all components of the modern education system (purpose, content, method, technology) and generates the need for their development. The issues of the introduction of computer technologies in the teaching of graphic

disciplines are investigated. The problems arising from this, and the search for possible ways to solve them. Conclusions are given about the need to develop an integrated course of geometric modeling, engineering and computer graphics and unified methodological approaches to the use of computer technology in the educational process, adaptation of the content of the course "computer graphics" applied to the block of general professional disciplines, taking into account interdisciplinary connections.

Keywords: 3ds Max, Blender, Google SketchUp, mind map, DiagrammaName, ArtRage.

Informatika va dasturlash sohasidagi zamonaviy o'quvchilarda texnik bilim va ko'nikmalar bilan bir ta'limning mazmuni, o'qitish shakllari va usullari, qatorda ijtimoiy va kasbiy muhitda ishlash imkonini vositalari va dasturlash metodologiyasini jadal beradigan malakalarni shakllantirish [1-3]. Shu yangilash vazifalari turibdi. Texnologiyaning, sababli, dasturlash bilan bog'liq ta'lim o'quv operatsion tizimlarning o'zgarishi, amaliy dasturlar dasturlarida muvaffaqiyatli jamoaviy ish, etakchilik va dasturlash tillarining murakkablashishi ta'lim va jamoani boshqarishni ta'minlaydigan o'quv tizimi uchun yangi muammolarni keltirib chiqarmoqda.mazmunini kiritish kerak.

Kompyuter dasturlarining doimiy ravishda murakkablashishi ularni ishlab chiqishda mavjud yondashuvlarni o'zgartirish zaruratini keltirib chiqaradi. Dasturiy ta'minotni yaratishning haqiqiy amaliyoti ko'plab xalqaro standartlar va korporativ me'yorlar bilan tartibga solinadi. Ko'rinib turibdiki, individual dasturlash murakkab dasturiy mahsulotlarni yaratishni ta'minlay olmaydi. Dasturiy ta'minot paketlari bo'yicha jamoaviy ish loyihani tashkil etish tamoyillariga asoslanadi: loyihaning hayot aylanishi, ishtirokchilarning rollari (rahbar, dizayner va boshqalar), bosqichlar. Rollarning har biri maktab va universitetda o'qish jarayonida shakllanishi kerak bo'lgan kompetensiyalar bilan bog'liq. Shu bilan birga, nafaqat benuqson dastur kodini ishlab chiqish, balki murakkab dasturiy tizimlar bo'yicha qo'shma loyiha ishlarida ishtirok etish imkoniyatiga ega bo'lgan mutaxassislarga talabning rivojlanishi sharoitida o'qituvchilar va o'quvchilar dasturlashni o'rgatishda.

Dasturlashda qo'llaniladigan asosiy tuzilmalar (chiziqli algoritm, tarmoqlanish, halqalar) kundalik hayotda muammoli bo'lishi mumkin emas, bizning faoliyatimizda doimo mavjud bo'lib, ular amalda odam tomonidan tushunilmaydi. Va faqat dasturlashni o'rgatishda bu holatlar o'quvchilarning diqqat-e'tiborini tortadi va ulardan maxsus metodologiya, maxsus fikrlash shakllariga ega bo'lishni talab qiladi [2]. So'rov shuni ko'rsatdiki, talabalar

dasturlashni o'rganishdagi asosiy muammolarni o'zlari nomlashadi: yangi ma'lumotlarning katta miqdori, dasturlash tili sintaksisini qo'llashda qat'iylik, asosiy matematik tayyorgarlik, izolyatsiyada uzoq vaqt ishlash zarurati, shuningdek, uzoq vaqt davomida dasturlarni ishlab chiqishda ruhiy zo'riqish va boshqalar. An'anaviy dasturlash mashg'ulotlari talabalarga muvaffaqiyatli jamoaviy ishlarni o'zlashtirish imkoniyatini bermaydi. Aksariyat ta'lim amaliyotlari texnik fanlarni o'rganishga qaratilgan akademik va nazariy xususiyatlar, o'qitish esa o'z bilim va tajribasini talabalarga etkazadigan o'qituvchiga (o'qituvchiga yo'naltirilgan yondashuv) qaratiladi [3]. Shuni inobatga olish kerakki, dasturlash nazariyasini an'anaviy o'qitish va algoritmlarni yaratish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish ham favqulodda vazifadir. Dasturlarni yaratish jarayoni ko'p sub'ektiv jarayonlarni tahlil qilish, o'z aqliy faoliyatini kuzatish, ichki jarayonlarni algoritmik tillar konstruktsiyalari bilan ko'rsatish kabi shaxsiy xususiyatlar va intellektual qobiliyatlarni talab qiladi.

Shunday qilib, dasturiy mahsulot ustida jamoaviy ishlashga tayyorlikni shakllantirish zarurati o'qituvchining allaqachon qiyin vazifasini sezilarli darajada murakkablashtiradi. Kasbiy va ilmiy metodik ishimizda bo'lajak informatika o'qituvchilari - "informatika" yo'nalishi bo'yicha pedagogik ta'lim bakalavriatlariga dasturlashni o'rgatish masalasiga alohida e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Bu ayniqsa muhimdir, chunki yaxshi uslubiy tayyorgarlik keyinchalik maktabda dasturlashni o'rgatishning zamonaviy yondashuvlarini amalga oshirishga imkon beradi. Bunday treningni o'tkazish uchun dasturlashni o'rgatish tajribasini eng muvaffaqiyatli o'quv markazlarida tahlil qilish tavsiya etiladi, ularning bu boradagi muvaffaqiyati yaqqol namoyon bo'ladi.

Internetning ta'lim mazmunini tahlil qilish shuni ta'kidlashga imkon beradiki, dasturlashni o'rgatish bo'yicha mualliflik yondashuvlarining eng keng tarqalishi, shuningdek, o'qitishning yuqori samaradorligi AQSh va Evropa universitetlari tomonidan taqdim etiladi. G'arbning ko'plab etakchi universitetlari dunyoning boshqa mintaqalaridan: Rossiya, AQSh, Xitoy, Hindiston, Osiyo va Afrikadan usullarni muvaffaqiyatli to'playdi va ishlab chiqadi.

Dasturlashni o'rgatishda interfaol texnologiyalardan foydalanish tajribasi. Xorijda dasturlashni o'qitish metodikasi sohasidagi asosiy innovatsion yo'nalishlar va bu yo'nalishlarni yetakchi universitetlarda tatbiq etish misollari keltirilgan.

Dasturlashda jamoaviy o'rganish tajribasi ancha xilma-xildir [3-5]. Yevropa universitetlarida turli yondashuvlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Misol uchun, Ispaniyada (Madridning Komplutense Universiteti) bir guruh o'qituvchilar

muammoli muloqot amaliyotini Ham, shaxslararo muloqot, nizolar va ularni hal qilish. NUCLEO tizimining ishlash tamoyillari faoliyat nazariyasiga asoslanadi va shaxsni rivojlantirish jarayonlarini o'rganish imkonini beruvchi virtual muhitda amalga oshiriladi. Ushbu muammoni hal qilish uchun o'qituvchi sub'ektning ijtimoiy muhitdagi xatti-harakatlarini modellashtirishi kerak. Tadqiqotchilar dasturiy mahsulotlarni jamoaviy ishlab chiqishni yaxshilash uchun NUCLEO dan foydalanishni taklif qilishadi. NUCLEO-da ijtimoiy o'zaro ta'sir ikki xil sxema orqali amalga oshiriladi: turli o'yin kontekstlarida motivatsiyani oshirish va guruh dinamikasini rivojlantirish uchun mo'ljallangan raqobat va hamkorlik, o'qituvchilar tomonidan tayyorlangan stsenariylar. Tizim talabalarning ta'lim yutuqlari tufayli erishiladigan mukofotlar va turli ijtimoiy darajalar ierarxiyasini amalga oshiradi [6].

Dasturlashni o'rgatishning o'yin kontseptsiyasi, masalan, kirish va chiqish ma'lumotlarining kombinatsiyasidan dastur qismlarini taxmin qilishni nazarda tutadi. Pex4Fun bu Microsoft Research (MSR) tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan brauzer o'yini. U turli kompyuter platformalari va qurilmalarida, shaxsiy kompyuterlardan smartfonlargacha ishlatilishi mumkin. Raqobat sharoitida talabalar o'qituvchi tomonidan qo'yilgan maqsadlarga erishib, C++ va VisualBasic dasturlashni o'rganishlari mumkin. Ushbu o'yin sizga ta'limning turli darajalarida -maktabdan universitetgacha dasturlashni o'rganish imkonini beradi. Ushbu o'yinning afzalliklari o'qituvchiga o'rganish strategiyasini o'zgartirish imkonini beradigan muammolarni hal qilishda va fikr-mulohazalarni hal qilishda guruh ishtirok etish imkoniyatini o'z ichiga oladi. Didaktik afzallik - g'ayrioddiy kombinatsiyalar imkoniyati Talabalar tomonidan yaratilgan algoritmik tuzilmalar uchun kirish ma'lumotlari, bu nafaqat muammoning echimini sinab ko'rishga imkon beradi, balki ularni yaratilgan kod fragmentini tushunish haqida o'ylashga majbur qiladi [5]. Biz fan (algoritmik) mazmun bilan to'yingan virtual ta'lim maydonlarini yaratishni dasturlashni o'qitishdagi innovatsion o'zgarishlar yo'nalishlaridan biri deb hisoblaymiz. Masalan, Second Life virtual olamlari (<http://secondlife.com>) universitetda dasturlashni jamoaviy o'rganish uchun ishlatilishi mumkin [7].

Loyiha modullarga bo'lingan va nafaqat protsessual, balki ob'ektga yo'naltirilgan dasturlashni ham o'rganish imkonini beradi. Trening davomida talabalar Elis kutubxonasi (odamlar, hayvonlar, mashinalar, binolar va boshqalar) 3D ob'ektlardan foydalangan holda oddiy animatsion filmlar va video o'yinlar yaratadilar. Elisning oddiy interfeysi sudrab olib tashlash texnologiyasiga asoslangan bo'lib, talabalarni odatiy ish turlaridan qutqaradi. Til ko'rsatmalari

Java, C++ va C# dasturlash tillaridagi standart ko'rsatmalarga mos keladi. Minerva CodeWitz (Finlyandiya) Yevropa loyihasi interaktiv ob'ektga yo'naltirilgan muhitda samarali dasturlashni o'rganishning innovatsion imkoniyatlarini ochib berish bilan bog'liq.

Asosiy algoritmik tuzilmalarning vizualizatsiyasi va muammolarni hal qilish misollarining ierarxik kutubxonasi talabalar uchun individual ta'lim yo'nalishlarini ishlab chiqish imkonini beradi. Ushbu loyihaning afzalliklari (o'rganishga an'anaviy yondashuvlarga nisbatan) Yevropaning yetakchi universitetlarining loyihada ishtirok etishi orqali o'quv materiallari to'plamlarini doimiy ravishda takomillashtirish, yangilash va kengaytirishni o'z ichiga oladi. Mualliflar o'quv jarayonida birlashtirilishi va o'qituvchilar va talabalarning qo'shimcha tayyorgarligisiz qo'llanilishi mumkin bo'lgan kichik, avtonom, portativ va hujjatlashtirilgan o'quv vazifalari kontseptsiyasini ishlab chiqadilar.

CodeWitz-dan dasturlashda o'quv vazifalari bo'yicha talabalarning jamoaviy ishini tashkil qilish uchun foydalanish mumkin va talabalarning Jamoa loyihalarida dasturlashni o'qitishni tashkil etishning yana bir istiqbolli yo'nalishi - bu ta'lim robototexnikasi. Ta'lim muassasalari uchun mavjud bo'lgan dasturlashtiriladigan kontrollerli qurilmalar turli darajadagi murakkablikdagi murakkab robot tizimlarini yaratishga imkon beradi - vizual algoritmik tuzilmalardan (MRDS 4, Scratch) zamonaviy dasturlash tillarigacha (C++, Java). AQShda yaratilgan RobotC platformasi (<http://www.robotc.net/>) dasturlashtiriladigan robototexnika uchun keng imkoniyatlarni taklif etadi, turli ishlab

chiqaruvchilarning robot qurilmalarini dasturlash imkonini beradi Dasturlash bo'yicha treningni tashkil qilish uchun RobotC o'rnatilgan RobotC Virtual World quyi tizimiga ega bo'lishi qulay, bu sizga virtual robot qurilmalarini boshqarish dasturlarini yaratishga imkon beradi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

1. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Matritsa rangi. Matritsa rangini tuzatish usullari. Fan va ta'lim, 2(8), 280-291. <http://openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1758> dan olindi.
2. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Matritsalar va ular ustida amallar. Fan va ta'lim, 2(8), 226-238. <http://openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1752> dan olindi.
3. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Vektorlar. Fan va ta'lim, 2(8), 173-182. <https://openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1747> dan olindi.

4. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar tizimini echishning matritsa, Gauss va Gauss-Jordan usullari. *Fan va ta'lim*, 2(8), 312-322. <http://openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1761> dan olindi.
5. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Chiziqli operatorlar va komissiya xossalari. *Fan va ta'lim*, 2(8), 133-145. <http://openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1744> dan olindi.
6. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Chiziqli operatorlar va komissiya xossalari. *Fan va ta'lim*, 2(8), 146-152. <http://openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1744> dan olindi.
7. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Kvadratik forma va uni kanonik korinishga keltirish. *Fan va ta'lim*, 2(8), 153-172. <https://www.openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1746> dan olindi.
8. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Arifmetik vektor fazo va unga misollar. *Fan va ta'lim*, 2(8), 109-120. <https://www.openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1742> dan olindi.
9. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Vektorlarning skalyar ko'paytmasi. *Fan va ta'lim*, 2(8), 183-191. <https://www.openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1748> dan olindi.
10. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Vektorlarning vektor va aralash ko'paytmalari. *Fan va ta'lim*, 2(8), 271-279. <http://openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1757> dan olindi.
11. Usmonov, M.T. & Shokirov.,Sh.H, (2022). Teylor formulasini matematik masalalarni echishdagi ahamiyati. "«Science and Education» Scientific Journal" *Scientific Journal*, Tom-3, 19-23.
12. Usmonov, M.T. & Shokirov.,Sh.H, (2022). Darajali qatorlarning taqribiy hisoblashlarga tatbiqi. «Science and Education» *Scientific Journal*, Tom-3, 29-32.
13. Usmonov, M.T. & Shokirov.,Sh.H, (2022). Ishoralari almashinib keluvchi qatorlar. Leybnits alomati. «Science and Education» *Scientific Journal*, Tom-3, 24-28.
14. Usmonov, M.T. & Shokirov.,Sh.H, (2022). Teylor qatori va uning tadbiqlari. «Science and Education» *Scientific Journal*, Tom-3, 33-38.
15. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Вычисление центра тяжести плоской ограниченной фигуры с помощью двойного интеграла. «Science and Education» *Scientific Journal*, Tom-2, 64-71.
16. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Биномиальное распределение вероятностей. «Science and Education» *Scientific Journal*, Tom-2, 81-85.

17. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Поток векторного поля. Поток через замкнутую поверхность. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 52-63.
18. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Вычисление определенного интеграла по формуле трапеций и методом Симпсона. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 213-225.
19. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Метод касательных. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 25-34.
20. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Вычисление предела функции с помощью ряда. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 92-96.
21. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Примеры решений произвольных тройных интегралов. Физические приложения тройного интеграла. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 39-51.
22. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Вычисление двойного интеграла в полярной системе координат. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 97-108.
23. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Криволинейный интеграл по замкнутому контуру. Формула Грина. Работа векторного поля. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 72-80.
24. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Правило Крамера. Метод обратной матрицы. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 249-255.
25. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Теоремы сложения и умножения вероятностей. Зависимые и независимые события. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 202-212.
26. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Распределение и формула Пуассона. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 86-91.
27. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Геометрическое распределение вероятностей. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 18-24.
28. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Вычисление площади поверхности вращения. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 97-104.
29. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Нахождение обратной матрицы. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 123-130.
30. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Вычисление двойного интеграла. Примеры решений. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 192-201.
31. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Метод прямоугольников. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 105-112.
32. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Как вычислить длину дуги кривой?. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 86-96.

33. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Вычисление площади фигуры в полярных координатах с помощью интеграла. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 77-85.
34. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Повторные пределы. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 35-43.
35. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Дифференциальные уравнения второго порядка и высших порядков. Линейные дифференциальные уравнения второго порядка с постоянными коэффициентами. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 113-122.
36. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Пределы функций. Примеры решений. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 139-150.
37. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Метод наименьших квадратов. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 54-65.
38. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Непрерывность функции двух переменных. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 44-53.
39. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Интегрирование корней (иррациональных функций). Примеры решений. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 239-248.
40. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Криволинейные интегралы. Понятие и примеры решений. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 26-38.
41. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Гипергеометрическое распределение вероятностей. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 19-25.
42. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Абсолютная и условная сходимость несобственного интеграла. Признак Дирихле. Признак Абеля. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 66-76.
43. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Решение систем линейных уравнений. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 131-138.
44. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Matritsalar va ular ustida amallar. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 226-238.
45. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Teskari matritsa. Teskari matritsani hisoblash usullari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 292-302.
46. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Bir jinsli chiziqqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasi. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 323-331.
47. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Chiziqqli fazo. Yevklid fazosi. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 121-132.
48. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Vektorlarning skalyar ko'paytmasi. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 183-191.

49. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Xos vektorlari bazis tashkil qiluvchi chiziqli operatorlar. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 146-152.
50. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasi va ularni echish usullari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 303-311.
51. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Vektorlar. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 173-182.
52. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Kvadratik forma va uni kanonik korinishga keltirish. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 153-172.
53. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Arifmetik vektor fazo va unga misollar. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 109-120.
54. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Chiziqli operatorlar va ularning xossalari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 133-145.
55. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Determinantlar nazariyasi. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 256-270.
56. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Matritsa rangi. Matritsa rangini hisoblash usullari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 280-291.
57. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Autentification, authorization and administration. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 233-242.
58. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Vektorlar nazariyasi elementlari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 332-339.
59. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). EHTIMOLLAR NAZARIYASI. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-1, 10-15.
60. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasi va ularni echish usullari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 333-311.
61. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Bir jinsli chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasi. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-21, 323-331.
62. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Vektorlar nazariyasi elementlari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 332-339.
63. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Chiziqli fazo. Yevklid fazosi. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 121-132.
64. Usmonov M. T. & Qodirov F. E, BIR JINSLI VA BIR JINSLIGA OLIB KELINADIGAN DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMALAR. AMALIY MASALALARGA TADBIQI (KO'ZGU MASALASI) , BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI: Vol. 2 No. 1 (2022): БАРҚАРОРЛИК ВА ЕТАКЧИ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ОНЛАЙН ИЛМИЙ ЖУРНАЛИ
65. Usmonov Maxsud Tulqin o'g'li, Sayifov Botirali Zokir o'g'li, Negmatova Nilufar Ergash qizi, Qodirov Farrux Ergash o'g'li, BIRINCHI VA IKKINCHI

TARTIBLI HUSUSIY HOSILALAR. TO'LA DIFFERENSIAL. TAQRIBIY HISOBLASH ,
BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI: 2022:
SPECIAL ISSUE: ZAMONAVIY UZLUKSIZ TA'LIM SIFATINI OSHIRISH
ISTIQBOLLARI

66. Usmonov Maxsud Tulqin o'g'li, Sayifov Botirali Zokir o'g'li, Negmatova
Nilufar Ergash qizi, Qodirov Farrux Ergash o'g'li, IKKI ARGUMENTLI
FUNKSIYANING ANIQLANISH SOHASI, GRAFIGI, LIMITI VA UZLUKSIZLIGI ,
BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI: 2022:
SPECIAL ISSUE: ZAMONAVIY UZLUKSIZ TA'LIM SIFATINI OSHIRISH
ISTIQBOLLARI

67. Usmonov Maxsud Tulqin o'g'li. (2022). FURYE QATORI. FUNKSIYALARNI
FURYE QATORIGA YOYISH. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6055125>

68. Usmonov. M. T. ., & Qodirov. F. E. . (2022). DARAJALI QATORLAR.
DARAJALI QATORLARNING YAQINLASHISH RADIUSI VA SOHASI. TEYLOR
FORMULASI VA QATORI. IJTIMOIIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY
JURNALI, 8–20. Retrieved from
<http://www.sciencebox.uz/index.php/jis/article/view/1151>

69. Usmonov. M. T. ., & Qodirov. F. E.. (2022). FURE QATORI VA UNING
TADBIQLARI. IJTIMOIIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 21–
33. Retrieved from <http://www.sciencebox.uz/index.php/jis/article/view/1152>

70. M.T Usmonov, M.A Turdiyeva, Y.Q Shoniyozova, (2021). SAMPLE POWER.
SELECTION METHODS (SAMPLE ORGANIZATION METHODS). ООО НАУЧНАЯ
ЭЛЕКТРОННАЯ БИБЛИОТЕКА , 59-60.

71. Усмонов,М.Т, М.А.Турдиева (2021). ГЛАВА 9. МЕТОДЫ И СРЕДСТВА
СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ЗАЩИТЫ КОМПЬЮТЕРНЫХ СЕТЕЙ. РИСКИ И ПРИНЦИПЫ
ЗАЩИТЫ ИНФОРМАЦИИ В ЭЛЕКТРОННОЙ ПОЧТЕ. ББК 60 С69, Ст-99.

72. Усмонов,М.Т, J.M.Saipnazarov, К.В. Ablaqulov (2021 SOLUTION OF
MATHEMATICAL PROBLEMS IN LOWER CLASSES. Книга: АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ
ВОПРОСЫ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКИ И ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ, 167-177.

73. Усмонов М.Т. (2022). E-LEARNING И ЕГО РОЛЬ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ
СИСТЕМЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ. : Special Issue_Та'limni modernizatsiyalash
jarayonlari muammolar va echimlar». 168-171.

74. Usmonov. M. T. ., & Qodirov. F. E.. (2022). STOKS FORMULASI. SIRT
INTEGRALLARI TADBIQLARI. IJTIMOIIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN
ILMIY JURNALI, 34–45. Retrieved from
<https://sciencebox.uz/index.php/jis/article/view/1153>

75. Usmonov M. T. The Concept of Compatibility, Actions on Compatibility. International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research (IJAMR), Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 10-13.
76. Usmonov M. T. The Concept of Number. The Establishment of the Concept of Natural Number and Zero. International Journal of Academic Information Systems Research (IJASIR), Vol. 4 Issue 12, December - 2020, Pages: 7-9.
77. Usmonov M. T. The Concept of Compatibility, Actions on Compatibility. International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS), Vol. 4 Issue 12, December - 2020, Pages: 66-68.
78. Usmonov M. T. General Concept of Mathematics and Its History. International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research (IJAMR). Vol. 4 Issue 12, December - 2020, Pages: 38-42
79. Usmonov M. T. Asymmetric Cryptosystems. International Journal of Academic Engineering Research (IJAER) ISSN: 2643-9085 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 6-9.
80. Usmonov M. T. Basic Concepts of Information Security. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 5-8.
81. Usmonov M. T. Communication Control Systems, Methodology. International Journal of Academic Engineering Research (IJAER) ISSN: 2643-9085 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 47-50.
82. Usmonov M. T. Compatibility between the Two Package Elements. Binar Relations and Their Properties. International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research (IJAMR) ISSN: 2643-9670 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 52-54.
83. Usmonov M. T. Cryptographic Protection of Information. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 24-26.
84. Usmonov M. T. Electronic Digital Signature. International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR) ISSN: 2643-9123 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 30-34.
85. Usmonov M. T. "Equal" And "Small" Relations. Add. Laws Of Addition. International Journal of Academic Information Systems Research (IJASIR) ISSN: 2643-9026 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 27-29.
86. Usmonov M. T. Establish Network Protection. International Journal of Academic Engineering Research (IJAER) ISSN: 2643-9085 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 14-21.

87. Usmonov M. T. Fundamentals of Symmetric Cryptosystem. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 36-40.
88. Usmonov M. T. General Concepts of Mathematics. International Journal of Academic Information Systems Research (IJAISR) ISSN: 2643-9026 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 14-16.
89. Usmonov M. T. Identification and Authentication. International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR) ISSN: 2643-9123 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 39-47.
90. Usmonov M. T. Information Protection and Its Types. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 1-4.
91. Usmonov M. T. Information Protection in Wireless Communication Systems. International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR) ISSN: 2643-9123 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 61-64.
92. Usmonov M. T. Information protection supply. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 12-15.
93. Usmonov M. T. Information Security Policy. International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR) ISSN: 2643-9123 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 70-73.
94. Usmonov M. T. Information War. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 79-82.
95. Usmonov M. T. International and National Legal Base in the Field Of Information Security. International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR) ISSN: 2643-9123 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 7-14.
96. Usmonov M. T. Legal Legislative Basis for Detection of Information Crime. International Journal of Academic Engineering Research (IJAER) ISSN: 2643-9085 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 80-87.
97. Usmonov M. T. Mathematical Proofs. Incomplete Induction, Deduction, Analogy. The Concept Of Algorithm And Its Properties. International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research (IJAMR) ISSN: 2643-9670 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 26-29.
98. Usmonov M. T. Means of Information Protection. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 27-30.

99. Usmonov M. T. Organization of E-Mail Protection. International Journal of Academic Engineering Research (IJAER) ISSN: 2643-9085 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 36-40.
100. Usmonov M. T. Organizing Internet Protection. International Journal of Academic Engineering Research (IJAER) ISSN: 2643-9085 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 24-28.
101. Usmonov M. T. Origin and Equal Strength Relationships between Sentences. Necessary and Sufficient Conditions. Structure of Theorem and Their Types. International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS) ISSN: 2643-640X Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 45-47.
102. Usmonov M. T. PhysicalSecurity. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 58-61.
103. Usmonov M. T. Practical Security Management. International Journal of Academic Engineering Research (IJAER) ISSN: 2643-9085 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 71-74.
104. Usmonov M. T. Problem Solving In Primary Schools. International Journal of Academic Information Systems Research (IJAISR) ISSN: 2643-9026 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 72-83.
105. Usmonov M. T. Reproduction. The Laws of Reproduction. International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS) ISSN: 2643-640X Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 36-40.
106. Usmonov M. T. Security Models. International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR) ISSN: 2643-9123 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 18-23.
107. Usmonov M. T. Solving Problems In Arithmetic Methods. International Journal of Academic Information Systems Research (IJAISR) ISSN: 2643-9026 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 58-61.
108. Usmonov M. T. Stenographic Protection of Information. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 31-35.
109. Usmonov M. T. Telecommunications and Network Security. International Journal of Academic Engineering Research (IJAER) ISSN: 2643-9085 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 57-61.
110. Usmonov M. T. The Concept of Compatibility, Actions on Compatibility. International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research (IJAMR) ISSN: 2643-9670 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 10-13.

111. Usmonov M. T. The Concept Of National Security. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 73-75.
112. Usmonov M. T. The Concept of Number. The Establishment of the Concept of Natural Number and Zero. International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research (IJAMR) ISSN: 2643-9670 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 18-21.
113. Usmonov M. T. The Concept of Relationship. Characteristics of Relationships. International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research (IJAMR) ISSN: 2643-9670 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 38-40.
114. Usmonov M. T. The Concept of Size and Measurement. International Journal of Academic Information Systems Research (IJASIR) ISSN: 2643-9026 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 36-40.
115. Usmonov M. T. The Emergence and Development of Methods of Writing All Negative Numbers. International Journal of Academic Information Systems Research (IJASIR) ISSN: 2643-9026 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 48-50.
116. Usmonov M. T. The Purpose, Function and History Of The Development Of Mathematical Science. International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS) ISSN: 2643-640X Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 8-17.
117. Usmonov M. T. True and False Thoughts, Quantities. International Journal of Academic Information Systems Research (IJASIR) ISSN: 2643-9026 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 1-5.
118. Usmonov M. T. Virtual Protected Networks. International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR) ISSN: 2643-9123 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 55-57.
119. Usmonov M. T. What Is Solving The Problem? Methods of Solving Text Problems. International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS) ISSN: 2643-640X Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 56-58.
120. M Усмонов - Academic research in modern science, 2022. КАК ПОСТРОИТЬ ЛИНИЮ В ПОЛЯРНОЙ СИСТЕМЕ КООРДИНАТ. Pages: 93-105.
121. UM Tulqin o'g'li - TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY ..., 2022. DETERMINANTLAR NAZARIYASI. Pages: 232-248.
122. R Jo'rayev, M Usmonov - Solution of social problems in management and ..., 2022. OZIQ-OVQAT SANOATINING DOLZARBLIGI VA SAMARADORLIGI. Pages: 19-25
123. M Усмонов - Academic research in modern science, 2022. КАК ПОСТРОИТЬ ЛИНИЮ В ПОЛЯРНОЙ СИСТЕМЕ КООРДИНАТ. Pages: 93-105

124. М Усмонов - Development and innovations in science, 2022. ВЕКТОРНОЕ ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЕ ВЕКТОРОВ. СМЕШАННОЕ ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЕ ВЕКТОРОВ. Pages: 33-52.
125. М Усмонов - Models and methods in modern science, 2022. ДИСКРЕТНЫЙ ВАРИАЦИОННЫЙ РЯД. ПОЛИГОН ЧАСТОТ И ЭМПИРИЧЕСКАЯ ФУНКЦИЯ РАСПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ. Pages: 27-35.
126. М Усмонов - Инновационные исследования в науке, 2022. ИНТЕРВАЛЬНЫЙ ВАРИАЦИОННЫЙ РЯД. ГИСТОГРАММА ОТНОСИТЕЛЬНЫХ ЧАСТОТ. Pages: 43-52
127. М Усмонов - Международная конференция академических наук, 2022. ФОРМУЛЫ ДЕЛЕНИЯ ОТРЕЗКА В ДАННОМ ОТНОШЕНИИ. ФОРМУЛЫ КООРДИНАТ СЕРЕДИНЫ ОТРЕЗКА. Pages: 17-26.
128. UM Tulqin o'g'li, QF Ergash o'g'li - TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY ..., 2022. YER OSTI SUVLARINING FIZIK XOSSALARI, KIMYOVIY TARKIBI, HARAKATI VA GRUNTLARNING SUV O'TKAZUVCHANLIGI, FILTRATSIYA QONUNI. Pages: 219-222.
129. UM Tulqin o'g'li, QF Ergash o'g'li - TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY ..., 2022. VEKTOR VA SKALYAR MAYDONLAR. GRADIYENT VA YO'NALISH BO'YICHA HOSILA. DIVERGENSIYA VA ROTOR. SATH CHIZIQLARI. GRADIYENT MAYDONLAR. OQIMLAR. Pages: 172-187.
130. UM Tulqin o'g'li, QF Ergash o'g'li - IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY ..., 2022. FURE QATORI VA UNING TADBIQLARI. Pages: 21-33.
131. o'g'li, U. M. T. ., & o'g'li, Q. F. E. . (2022). FURE QATORI VA UNING TADBIQLARI. IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 21-33. Retrieved from <http://sciencebox.uz/index.php/jis/article/view/1152>
132. o'g'li, U. M. T. ., & o'g'li, Q. F. E. . (2022). DARAJALI QATORLAR. DARAJALI QATORLARNING YAQINLASHISH RADIUSI VA SOHASI. TEYLOR FORMULASI VA QATORI. IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 8-20. Retrieved from <http://www.sciencebox.uz/index.php/jis/article/view/1151>
133. МТЎ Усмонов, ХУМ Ўғли - Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary ..., 2022. РАВНОМЕРНОЕ РАСПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ ВЕРОЯТНОСТЕЙ. 15-24
134. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasi va ularni yechish usullari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
135. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Bir jinsli chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasi. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.

136. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Vektorlar nazariyasi elementlari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
137. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Chiziqli fazo. Yevklid fazosi. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
138. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Matritsa rangi. Matritsa rangini hisoblash usullari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
139. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Matritsalar va ular ustida amallar. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
140. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Maxsud Tulqin o 'g'li Usmonov maqsudu32@ gmail. com Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universiteti Qarshi filiali. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
141. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Teskari matritsa. Teskari matritsani hisoblash usullari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
142. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Chiziqli operatorlar va ularning xossalari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
143. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Xos vektorlari bazis tashkil qiluvchi chiziqli operatorlar. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
144. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Kvadratik forma va uni kanonik korinishga keltirish. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
145. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Arifmetik vektor fazo va unga misollar. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
146. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Vektorlarning skalyar ko 'paytmasi. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
147. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Determinantlar nazariyasi. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
148. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Vektorlarning vektor va aralash ko 'paytmalari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.